

Determining the True Tensile Failure Strain of Carbon Fibre Composites and Factors Affecting it

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Failure of Composites

- After >50 years, there are still many unresolved issues with measuring and predicting failure
- A recent paper highlighted the difficulties of performing accurate testing:

“The data of these observed behaviors must be completely uncorrupted by the inadvertent and uncontrolled influences that almost inevitably creep in.”

- How to generate high quality data for tensile failure of unidirectional carbon fibre/epoxy?
- Use of proposed test method to examine the factors affecting the failure strain

Invited Guest Editorial

Why progress on the failure of fiber composite materials has been so retarded

Richard M Christensen
Stanford University, Stanford, USA

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An accurate simple tensile test

- Standard methods underestimate tensile strength due to stress concentrations at grips
- Hybrids can eliminate stress concentration

Czél, Jalalvand, Wisnom, 2016

An accurate simple tensile test

- Consistent gauge section failures
- Much higher failure strain
- 1.86% vs. 1.5% for TR30 carbon
- Gauge section failure even without end-tabs

Effect of shear on tensile failure strain

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- Test carbon angle plies to generate shear and tension
- Glass plies suppress failure at end tabs
- Thin carbon plies suppress shear cracks and free edge delamination
- Should obtain gauge failure uninfluenced by other modes

Layups

- Skyflex TC35 carbon/epoxy, 0.03 mm ply thickness
- Hexcel E glass, 0.127 mm plies, $[0_G/\pm\theta_C]_S$
- Carbon layups: $[0]_S$, $[\pm 5]_S$, $[\pm 10]_S$, $[\pm 15]_S$, $[\pm 20]_S$, $[\pm 25]_S$

- The shear strain value increases with θ but σ_2 is almost 0.

Jalalvand, Fotouhi, Leong, Wisnom, 2017

Test results

- Successful gauge section failure
- Single fracture followed by catastrophic delamination
- Acoustic Emission shows no significant signal before failure
- Strains measured with video extensometer

Failure development-
[0_{2EG}/±15_C]s layup

Failure strain

- Fibre direction tensile failure strain is not significantly affected by shear strain
- In multidirectional laminates could not reach such high shear strains without fibre failure in other plies

q	fibre direction strain (%)	Shear strain (%)	CV for fibre direction strain
0	1.834	0	1.09%
5	1.853	0.436	3.99%
10	1.797	0.88	2.58%
15	1.818	1.402	1.76%
20	1.766	1.948	4.37%
25	1.654	2.528	4.41%

Low CV

Effect of transverse compression

- Use thin carbon angle plies to induce transverse compression in central 0 plies
- Lower modulus angle plies replace glass, prevent grip failure
- Skyflex TC33 carbon/epoxy $[\pm 15_6/0_2]_s$ $[\pm 20_6/0_2]_s$ $[\pm 28_6/0_2]_s$

Failure strain

- $[\pm 15_6/0_2]_s$ initial grip failure
- Glass plies added
- All gauge section failures
- Strains measured with video extensometer
- Correction for Poisson and thermal strains
- No effect of transverse compression on fibre failure strain

Rev, Czél, Wisnom, 2018

Lay-up	Long. Strain at failure [%]	Trans. Strain at failure [%]	Stress at failure [MPa]	Transverse compressive stress [MPa]
0	1.62	-0.04	1696.3	0.00
$[SG_2/\pm 15_6/0_2]_s$	1.60	-1.05	1069.3	-36.50
$[\pm 20_6/0_2]_s$	1.62	-2.84	1052.6	-141.48
$[\pm 28_6/0_2]_s$	1.62	-2.91	622.4	-142.40

Hybrid effect with thin plies

- Most failure criteria ignore the effect of ply thickness or adjacent plies on tensile strain at failure
- Tests carried out on TR30 high strength carbon/epoxy sandwiched between S-glass plies to investigate
- TR30 ply thickness 0.03mm, S-glass 0.155mm
- Specimens with 3 or 4 plies delaminated, as previously shown

Specimens with 1 or 2 carbon plies

- Delamination suppressed
- Plateau at ~1100 MPa
- Carbon ply fragmentation
- Final failure of glass at 3.5%

Defining failure strain

- Take intersection of fitted lines – fragmentation established
- Small correction of about -0.03% for thermal strains

Effect of ply thickness

- 2.23% corrected failure strain for single very thin ply
- Hybrid effect of 20% over baseline of 1.86%
- No effect for ply thickness greater than 0.08mm

← Baseline strain from delaminating hybrids

Wisnom, Czél, Swolfs, Jalalvand, Gorbatiikh, Verpoest, 2016

Explanation for hybrid effect

- Formation of first critical cluster of fibres delayed

- Model by Yentl Swolfs captures the effect quite well

Wisnom, Czél, Swolfs, Jalalvand,
Gorbatikh, Verpoest, 2016

Effect of specimen size

- SK thin TC35/K50 carbon/epoxy prepreg (0.024 mm)
Hexcel S2-glass/913 epoxy (0.155 mm)
- All dimensions and displacement rates scaled

Lay-up sequence (SG: S-glass, TC35: Carbon)	No. of spec.	Nominal carbon layer thickn.	Nominal width	Nominal gauge length
Scaled test configs.:		[mm]	[mm]	[mm]
[SG₂/TC35₂]_s	10	0.095	5	30
[SG₄/TC35₄]_s	11	0.190	10	60
[SG₈/TC35₈]_s	10	0.379	20	120
[SG₁₆/TC35₁₆]_s	6	0.758	40	240

Test results

- Failure strain taken at load drop when carbon fractures
- Consistent gauge section failures
- -0.025% correction for thermal stress
- 23% reduction in strength for factor of 8 increase in linear dimensions (factor of 512 on volume)
- Low variability: CV 3-5%

Wisnom, Cantera, Czél, Jalalvand, 2017

Lay-up sequence	Carbon layer failure strain [%] (CV rel.%)
$[SG_2/TC35_2]_s$	2.028 (3.6)
$[SG_4/TC35_4]_s$	1.854 (4.9)
$[SG_8/TC35_8]_s$	1.784 (2.6)
$[SG_{16}/TC35_{16}]_s$	1.560 (5.4)

Weibull modulus

- Weibull modulus m determined from slope of log-log plot
- Value of $m=25.0$ consistent with other reported values for high strength carbon
e.g. $m=25$ from scaled flexural tests (Wisnom, 1991)

Conclusions

- Challenges in obtaining reliable experimental data - strain underestimated, even for “simple” fibre direction tensile failure
- Possible to achieve consistent gauge section tensile failure using hybrid specimens
- Failure strain is insensitive to shear and transverse compression
- Ply thickness and specimen volume can cause changes in failure strain of more than 20%
- Are conventional failure criteria addressing the most important issues?

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Thanks for your attention!

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